

Synthesis, spectral, thermal and antimicrobial studies of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes of Schiff base derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone

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Abstract : Some novel metal complexes of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) with a Schiff base derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR, UV-Visible, ¹H NMR and ESR spectral studies. The X-ray diffraction studies of the complex [MoO(AAPDHA)Cl₃] (where AAPDHA = aminoantipyrine dihydroxyacetophenone) indicated orthorhombic crystal lattice with unit cell dimensions *a* = 6.3314 Å, *b* = 8.5059 Å and *c* = 15.405 Å. The thermal behaviour of one of the complexes has also been examined. The ligand and the complexes were screened for their possible antibacterial and antifungal activities. The Schiff base ligand behaves as a neutral bidentate chelating agent in all the complexes, coordinating through carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. The complexes have distorted octahedral geometry.

Keywords : Oxomolybdenum(V), dioxomolybdenum(VI), Schiff base, 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone.

Introduction

The chemistry of molybdenum has aroused considerable interest in view of its biochemical importance¹. The higher oxidation states of molybdenum are dominated by oxogroups bound to molybdenum. Both Mo^V and Mo^{VI} form a large number of oxo and dioxocomplexes with polydentate chelating ligands. Synthetic flexibility of Schiff bases may permit the synthesis of multidentate ligands of diverse structural type. The Schiff bases possess anticancer, antibacterial properties and have important effect to stimulate enzymes². In view of the importance of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes, we have isolated and characterized some new oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes of a potential multidentate Schiff base derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone (AAPDHA) (Fig. 1).

Results and discussion

All the chelates are deeply coloured and non-hygroscopic solids. They are soluble in methanol, ethanol and partially soluble in water and insoluble in ether and benzene. The analytical and spectroscopic data (Tables 1 and 2) showed that all the complexes are mononuclear with

AAPDHA

Fig. 1

general formula [MoO(L)XCl₂] and [MoO₂(L)XCl], where L = AAPDHA (aminoantipyrine dihydroxyacetophenone) and X = Cl, NCS, NO₃, ClO₄. The molecular weights of the compounds (measured by Rast's method) are also in good agreement with these formulations. The molar conductance values of the complexes measured for 10⁻³ M solution in nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and methanol (Table 1) adequately confirm the non-electrolytic³ nature of the metal complexes. All the oxomolybdenum(V) complexes show magnetic moment values in the range 1.69–1.75 B.M., which is nearer to the spin-only value for oxoMo^V complexes. This shows the absence of any Mo–Mo interaction in these complexes⁴. All the dioxomolybdenum(VI)

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the molybdenum complexes

Ligand/Compd.	Colour	Mol. wt.	M.p. (°C)	% Mo Obsd./ (Calcd.)	Molar conductance (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
					C ₆ H ₅ NO ₂	CH ₃ CN	CH ₃ OH	
AAPDHA	Yellow	348 (337.4)	230	-	-	-	-	-
[MoO(AAPDHA)Cl ₃]	Orange red	570 (555.7)	285	17.24 (17.27)	10.2	5.0	12.1	1.69
[MoO(AAPDHA)(NCS)Cl ₂]	Yellowish red	592 (578.3)	293	16.55 (16.59)	9.6	5.8	9.3	1.74
[MoO(AAPDHA)(NO ₃)Cl ₂]	Chocolate brown	593 (582.2)	288	16.41 (16.48)	10.4	4.7	9.7	1.71
[MoO(AAPDHA)(ClO ₄)Cl ₂]	Orange red	631 (619.7)	302	15.31 (15.48)	9.9	5.5	10.3	1.75
[MoO ₂ (AAPDHA)Cl ₂]	Brown	521 (536.2)	320	17.81 (17.89)	6.7	8.2	5.8	Diamagnetic
[MoO ₂ (AAPDHA)(NCS)Cl]	Yellowish red	569 (558.8)	310	17.15 (17.17)	8.1	3.6	5.9	Diamagnetic
[MoO ₂ (AAPDHA)(NO ₃)Cl]	Chocolate brown	580 (562.7)	324	17.01 (17.05)	7.5	8.5	8.3	Diamagnetic
[MoO ₂ (AAPDHA)(ClO ₄)Cl]	Brown	611 (600.2)	305	15.92 (15.98)	9.1	7.1	5.7	Diamagnetic

All complexes gave satisfactory C, H, N, S and anion analyses.

Table 2. Spectral data of the ligand (AAPDHA) and oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes

Ligand/Complexes	Infrared assignments (cm ⁻¹)							
	ν_{OH}	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{sym(O=Mo=O)}}$	$\nu_{\text{asym(O=Mo=O)}}$	$\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Mo-O}}$
AAPDHA	2975	1648	1592	-	-	-	-	-
[MoO(AAPDHA)Cl ₃]	3401	1604	1543	960	-	-	567	450
[MoO(AAPDHA)(NCS)Cl ₂]	3422	1610	1544	968	-	-	569	440
[MoO(AAPDHA)(NO ₃)Cl ₂]	3400	1614	1568	960	-	-	590	440
[MoO(AAPDHA)(ClO ₄)Cl ₂]	3409	1602	1568	955	-	-	569	422
[MoO ₂ (AAPDHA)Cl ₂]	3410	1612	1560	-	958	906	569	410
[MoO ₂ (AAPDHA)(NCS)Cl]	3429	1623	1550	-	947	910	571	425
[MoO ₂ (AAPDHA)(NO ₃)Cl]	3405	1602	1546	-	945	910	565	422
[MoO ₂ (AAPDHA)(ClO ₄)Cl]	3383	1606	1560	-	956	903	592	419

complexes are found to be diamagnetic as expected for a d^0 -system.

Infrared spectra :

The selected vibrational bands and assignments of the ligand and the metal complexes are listed in Table 2. The infrared spectrum of the free ligand exhibited a broad band of medium intensity at ~ 2975 cm⁻¹, assignable to hydrogen bonded -OH group⁵. This band disappears on complexation in all the cases. A broad medium intensity band observed at ~ 3400 cm⁻¹ confirming the presence of free -OH groups and their non-participation in co-

ordination with the metal ion. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (azomethine) observed at 1648 and 1592 cm⁻¹ respectively, in the spectrum of the Schiff base ligand show a downward shift (~ 1610 and ~ 1560 cm⁻¹) in all the complexes⁶. These suggest participation of the pyrazol-carbonyl and azomethine groups in coordination. Thus the ligand acts as a neutral bidentate coordinating through the $>\text{C=O}$ and $>\text{C=N}$ groups only.

In the spectra of all the oxomolybdenum(V) complexes, a very strong band at 960 cm⁻¹ corresponds to Mo=O stretching frequency^{5,7} is observed. Strong bands exhi-

bited by dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes in the region 940–960 and 900–915 cm^{-1} are attributed to ν_{sym} ($\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O}$) and ν_{asym} ($\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O}$) respectively of *cis*- MoO_2 moiety⁸. MoO_2 prefers to form a *cis* configuration due to maximum utilization of the available $d\pi$ orbitals for bonding with the oxo groups. The weak band observed at 565 cm^{-1} in the spectra of these complexes can be attributed to $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}^4$. Medium intensity new bands appeared at 420 and 410 cm^{-1} in oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes respectively are attributed to $\nu_{\text{Mo-O}}$.

The *N*-coordinated nature⁹ of the thiocyanate group is indicated by the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ ($\sim 2067 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ ($\sim 770 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and δ_{NCS} ($\sim 466 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) bands. The bands at 1531 (ν_4) and 1410 cm^{-1} (ν_1) with a separation of 121 cm^{-1} suggest mono coordinated nitrate group¹⁰.

A very strong band at 630 cm^{-1} and a medium intensity band at 1140 cm^{-1} observed in the spectrum of the perchlorate complexes are assigned to ν_3 and ν_4 respectively indicating a monodentately coordinated perchlorate group¹¹.

NMR spectra :

In the ^1H NMR spectra of the ligand and one of the $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}]$ complexes (Figs. 2 and 3), sharp multiple signals of the aromatic protons are observed in the region δ 6.80–7.31. The signals due to $>\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ protons and $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$ protons are observed at δ 2.11 and 2.34 respectively. In the ligand AAPDHA and its complex, the signal due to -OH proton is present

in the region δ 10.82. The presence of -OH signal both in the ligand and its complex indicates its non-involvement in coordination¹².

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectral bands of the present oxomolybdenum(V) complexes show similar absorption peaks. A strong intense band observed in the region 26178–25974 cm^{-1} is attributed to $O(\pi) \rightarrow d(\text{Mo})$. The band due to the transition $^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2A_1$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) is probably masked by the above bands. The spectra of the complexes exhibit two more bands, a medium intensity band at 21052–19231 cm^{-1} and a weak broad band, spread over the region 14792–13596 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to $^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2B_1$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) and $^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2E$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$) respectively. The electronic spectra thus indicate an octahedral environment for all the complexes and are in conformity with the Ballhausen-Gray scheme for an octahedral geometry¹³. No bands are observed below 10000 cm^{-1} and hence the possibility of a tetrahedral structure can be ruled out. The complexes can be best considered as octahedral with strong tetragonal distortion, resulting from the $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ multiple bond.

ESR spectra :

The ESR spectrum of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}_2]$ recorded in polycrystalline form at room temperature, exhibited a single line only. The ESR parameters were calculated and found to be $g_{\parallel} = 1.965$, $g_{\perp} = 1.997$ and $g_{\text{av}} = 1.986$. The g_{av} value indicates the complex to be monomeric with Mo in the pentavalent state¹⁴.

Fig. 2. NMR spectrum of ligand AAPDHA.

Fig. 3. NMR spectrum of $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}]$.

Thermal studies :

The thermal decomposition behaviour of complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}_2]$ have been studied using TG and DTG techniques in an atmosphere of air at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The decomposition of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}_2]$ occur in two stages as indicated by the DTG peaks at 311 and $428\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The first stage of decomposition corresponds to the initial weight loss of ligand molecule and two Cl^- ions in the temperature range of $270\text{--}350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The second step of decompo-

sition at $360\text{--}440\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ can be attributed to the loss of remaining part leading to the formation of stable metal oxide, MoO_3 . The percentage mass loss in TG (24.16%) agrees well with the theoretical value (24.78%) (Fig. 4). The order parameters for the first and second stages of decomposition are two.

The Coats and Redfern methods¹⁵ have been used for finding the kinetic parameters of the complexes. The fractional weight loss and corresponding $(1 - \alpha)^n$ values have been calculated from the TG curves at different tempera-

Fig. 4. TG and DTG curves of $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}_2]$.

tures where 'n' depends upon the reaction model and a dimensionless quantity 'α' is employed for monitoring the reaction from mass loss,

$$\alpha = \frac{W_0 - W_t}{W_0 - W_f}$$

The decomposition of the complexes have been observed to follow first order kinetics as evident from the linear plot of $-\log [-\log (1 - \alpha)/T^2]$ vs $1/T$. The values of intercept, slope and hence the activation energy (E_a) were obtained from the plots. The values of pre-exponential factor (A) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) were calculated from the equation and found that $A = \log AR/\beta E_a$ and $\Delta S^* = 2.303 R \log Ah/kT$ (where k is Boltzman constant, T the peak temperature and β the heating rate). The energy of activation of first and second stages of

decomposition are found to be 174.06 and 227.45 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The value of ΔS for the two stages of decomposition are 794.9 and 754.2 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively¹⁵. The computational details and the kinetic parameters of the two stages of thermal decomposition of the complex are given in Tables 3, 4 and 5, respectively.

X-Ray diffraction studies :

The X-ray diffraction studies of the complex [MoO(AAPDHA)Cl₃] have been carried out (Fig. 5) using CuK_α radiation with $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$. The main peaks have been indexed (Table 6) and the d_{hkl} values were compared with the calculated ones using Hesse and Lipson's procedure¹⁶. The observed values fit well with orthorhombic system to give a unit cell with dimensions $a = 6.3314 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 8.5059 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 15.405 \text{ \AA}$. The number of molecules per unit cell was found to be four.

Table 3. Computational details of the first stage of thermal decomposition of [MoO(AAPDHA)(NO₃)Cl₂]

T (°C)	M (mg)	TK	$r = 0.99659$		α	gα	CR
			RT	W (mg)			
270	82.5	543	1.84162	0	0	0	-
280	79.1	553	1.80832	3.4	0.11184	0.12593	-14.7027
290	76.8	563	1.7762	5.7	0.1875	0.23077	-14.1329
300	72.6	573	1.7452	9.9	0.32566	0.48293	-13.4296
310	69.2	583	1.71527	13.3	0.4375	0.77778	-12.9876
320	64.5	593	1.68634	18	0.59211	1.45161	-12.3977
330	59	603	1.65837	23.5	0.77303	3.4058	-11.5783
340	56.2	613	1.63132	26.3	0.86513	6.41463	-10.9781

Table 4. Computational details of the second stage of thermal decomposition of [MoO(AAPDHA)(NO₃)Cl₂]

T (°C)	M (mg)	TK	$r = 0.99713$		α	gα	CR
			RT	W (mg)			
360	46	633	1.57978	0	0	0	-
370	43.8	643	1.55521	2.2	0.1375	0.15942	-14.7685
380	41.6	653	1.53139	4.4	0.275	0.37931	-13.9325
390	39.2	663	1.5083	6.8	0.425	0.73913	-13.2958
400	37.3	673	1.48588	8.7	0.54375	1.19178	-12.8480
410	34.5	683	1.46413	11.5	0.71875	2.55556	-12.1147
420	33.1	693	1.443	12.9	0.80625	4.16129	-11.6562

Table 5. Kinetic parameters for two stages of thermal decomposition of [MoO(AAPDHA)(NO₃)Cl₂]

Stages	Peak temp. (K)	Activation energy, E_a (kJ/mol)	Pre-exponential factor, A (s ⁻¹)	Entropy of activation, ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
1	584.2	174.0577	3.629×10^{13}	794.982
2	701.06	227.452	5.839×10^{15}	754.257

Fig. 5. X-Ray diffraction patterns of $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})\text{Cl}_3]$.Table 6. X-Ray diffraction data of $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})\text{Cl}_3]$

Line	<i>h k l</i>	$\sin^2\theta$		Relative intensity (%)
		Obsd.	Calcd.	
1	1 0 0	0.0151	0.0148	10.41
2	0 1 2	0.0196	0.0182	22.31
3	1 1 0	0.0232	0.0230	100.00
4	0 1 3	0.0291	0.0307	48.54
5	0 2 0	0.0319	0.0328	47.00
6	0 2 1	0.0343	0.0353	34.89
7	1 0 3	0.0374	0.0373	31.46
8	1 2 0	0.0476	0.0476	49.44
9	1 0 4	0.0536	0.0548	34.39

Antimicrobial studies :

The antibacterial activities of the ligand (AAPDHA) and its complexes $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})\text{Cl}_3]$, $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}]$ were tested against *Enterobacter aerogenes* ATCC 12666, *E. coli* ATCC 25922, *Salmonella typhi* ATCC 35987, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* ATCC 10796, *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 51912 and *Serratia marcescens* ATCC 12294 by disc diffusion method¹⁷ at concentration of 10 μg per disc using penicillin as positive control and chloroform as negative control. The test results show that the Schiff base ligand did not possess any antibacterial property but the complexes showed antibacterial activities.

The ligand (AAPDHA) and two complexes $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})\text{Cl}_3]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}]$ were screened for their possible antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus* ATCC 1027 and *Penicillium sp.* ATCC 10115 by disc diffusion method at a concentration of 10 μg per disc using Gresiofulvin as positive control and chloroform as negative control. The test results show that the ligand AAPDHA did not show any antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus* and *Penicillium sp.* But the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPDHA})\text{Cl}_3]$ showed antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus* at a concentration of 10 μg per disc giving a zone of inhibition of 10 mm and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPDHA})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}]$ showed antifungal activity against *Penicillium sp.* giving a zone of inhibition of 15 mm, at the concentration tested.

Experimental

MoCl_5 (Aldrich Chemicals, USA), 4-aminoantipyrine (E. Merck, Germany), 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone (Sisco Research Laboratory, Bombay) and MoO_3 (Lobochemie, Bombay) were used as such. All other used chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Metal, halide and sulphur in the complexes were estimated by standard methods¹⁸. Perchlorate was estimated by Kurz's method¹⁹. Elemental analyses were carried out at SAIF, Kochi. Molecular weights were determined by Rast's method, using biphenyl as solvent. The purity of compounds were checked by TLC. The IR spectra were

recorded using KBr pellets in the 4000–400 cm^{-1} region on a Shimadzu IR Prestige-21 spectrometer and the electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 3101 PC UV/Vis-NIR scanning spectrophotometer at NIIST, Thiruvananthapuram. The molar conductances of the complexes in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$, CH_3OH and CH_3CN (*ca.* 10^{-3} M) were measured using an Elico CM 82T conductivity bridge with a dip-type cell, fitted with Pt-electrode. ^1H NMR spectrum of the ligand and its complex were recorded in CDCl_3 on a 300 MHz Bruker Avance-300 NMR spectrometer, using TMS as reference at VSSC, Thiruvananthapuram. ESR spectra of one of the complexes was run on a Varian E-112X-Q band spectrometer with DPPH as a reference material at IIT, Chennai. Magnetic susceptibility at room temperature (300 ± 2 K) was measured on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant at University of Kerala, Kariavattom. Thermogravimetric curve of complex was recorded on a Mettler TG-50 thermobalance at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in air at VSSC, Thiruvananthapuram. The X-ray powder diffraction patterns were obtained on Philips X-ray diffractometer at NIIST, Thiruvananthapuram (PW 1710) using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation with $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$. Antibacterial and antifungal nature of the ligand and the complexes were tested by disc diffusion method.

Synthesis of ligand :

The ligand AAPDHA was synthesized from 4-aminoantipyrine and 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone by refluxing their equimolar solutions in methanol on a water bath for *ca.* 1–2 h. On cooling, bright yellow crystals of AAPDHA were obtained. The crystals were filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised with hot methanol and dried *in vacuo* at ambient temperature (yield 85%).

Synthesis of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes :

Oxomolybdenum(V) complexes : The chloride complex was prepared by adding a methanolic solution of MoCl_5 (2 mmol) to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol) with vigorous stirring (1 : 1 ratio) after adjusting the pH ~ 5 using sodium acetate/acetic acid buffer. The resultant solution was heated on a water bath for ~ 1 h. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo* (orange red, yield 70%).

The following general method was adopted for the preparation of the thiocyanate, nitrate and perchlorate complexes. By adding a methanolic solution of MoCl_5 (2 mmol) containing ~ 0.5 g of NH_4CNS or ~ 0.5 g LiNO_3 or 3–4 drops of HClO_4 to a hot methanolic solution of the

ligand (2 mmol) with vigorous stirring after adjusting the pH ~ 5 using sodium acetate/acetic acid buffer. The resulting solution was heated over a water bath for ~ 1 h. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed several times with methanol and then dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo* [Thiocyanate complex (yellowish red, 75%); nitrate complex (chocolate brown, 75%) and perchlorate complex (orange red, 70%)].

Dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes : MoO_3 was dissolved in hot conc. HCl. The solution was added dropwise with stirring to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol) after adjusting the pH ~ 5 using sodium acetate/acetic acid buffer and refluxed for ~ 1 h. The solid separated on concentrating the solution was filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo* (brown, yield 75%).

The following general method was adopted for the preparation of the thiocyanate, nitrate and perchlorate complexes. MoO_3 (2 mmol) was dissolved in hot concentrated HCl and to this ~ 0.5 g $\text{NH}_4\text{CNS}/0.5$ g $\text{LiNO}_3/3$ –4 drops of HClO_4 was added. The resulting solution was stirred with a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol) after adjusting the pH ~ 5 using sodium acetate/acetic acid buffer and refluxed for ~ 1 h. The solid separated on concentrating the solution was filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo* [Thiocyanate complex (yellowish red, 80%); nitrate complex (chocolate brown, 75%) and perchlorate complex (brown, 78%)].

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